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DETERMINATION & VALIDATION OF PROPRONOLOL IN HUMAN PLASMA BY ELECTOSPRAY IONIZATION-MASS SPECTROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

A rapid, specific and accurate high performance liquid chromatographic method for the determination of propranolol in K₂EDTA human plasma using tramadol as internal standard was developed and validated using an Electrospray Ionization (ESI)-mass spectrometry detection. The extraction process involved a solid phase extraction. Both propranolol and the internal standard were eluted under isocratic mode using a Inertsil 50 X 4.6 mm i.d, 5 μm column. The mobile phase composed a mixture of 10:90 % v/v 5mM ammonium acetate solution and acetonitrile at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/minute. The injection volume is 5 μL. The runtime of the method is 2 minutes. The method showed good linearity in the range of 1.000 – 402.171 ng/mL. The mean recovery of propranolol from all the quality control samples is 65.83 % with a % coefficient of variation of 7.38 % and recovery of internal standard was 82.12% with a % coefficient of variation of 3.37 %. Matrix effects were not observed. The method is validated as per ICH guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION

Propranolol (Fig. 1A), 1-(isopropylamino)-3-(1-naphthoxy)-2-propanol, is a non-selective beta-adrenergic receptor blocking agent and is highly effective as an antihypertensive and antianginal drug. It possesses no other autonomic nervous system activity and specifically competes with beta-adrenergic receptor-stimulating agents for available receptor sites. The drug is widely used in clinical practice for the treatment of cardiac arrhythmia, hypertension and angina pectoris [1], dysfunctional labour and anxiety [2, 3]. It is included as a drug of abuse by the international Olympic committee due to its activity of reducing cardiac, contraction, heart rate and coronary blood flow [4, 5]. Monitoring of propranolol in biological fluids is important not only in clinical practice but also in the field of doping control. Propranolol is subjected to extensive and highly variable hepatic first-pass metabolism following oral administration, with a bioavailability of between 15% and 23% [6]. Prolonged release formulations may reduce the dosing frequency [7-9], but the bioavailability of propranolol from these formulations is only 40%–60% of that from a conventional tablet. This has been attributed to the slower absorption in the gastrointestinal tract coupled with an extensive first-pass effect [10, 11].

Two HPLC methods [12, 13] have been developed for the determination of propranolol in raw materials or pharmaceutical formulations. Several other analytical methods, including GC [14], HPLC [15-17], TLC [18], and capillary electrophoresis [19], have been reported for the determination of propranolol in biological fluids (including human plasma, whole blood and urine), in which the most sensitive analytical method reported has a lowest limit of quantification (LLOQ) as low as 1.3 ng/ml. A pilot 40-mg dose pharmacokinetic study of propranolol hydrochloride sustained-release tablets showed that the plasma concentration of propranolol in the terminal elimination phase might be below 1 ng/ml. So, the analytical methods reported in the literature are unable to meet the requirements for a pharmacokinetic study of propranolol. To evaluate the pharmacokinetics of propranolol hydrochloride sustained-release tablets in humans, a more sensitive and simple method is required. This paper described the development and validation of a sensitive and rapid LC-ESI-MS method using a narrow-bore column which could improve the sensitivity with an LLOQ as low as 1.0 ng/ml for the quantification of propranolol in human plasma, using 0.5 ml human plasma samples. The method has been validated as per ICH guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Solvents and Chemicals

Propranolol (USP 99.8 % w/w) was purchased from Varda Biotech Pvt Ltd (Mumbai, India). Tramadol is kindly provided by Vijaya Sri Organics Pvt Ltd (used as Internal Standard, Purity 99.0 % w/w). HPLC grade Acetonitrile, Ammonium acetate is purchased from Merck, Mumbai. Deionized water was processed through a Milli-Q water purification system (Millipore, USA). All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

Chromatographic System & Instrument Parameters

The Chromatographic system consisted of a Shimadzu LC-20AD pump, SIL HTC Auto sampler, CTO-10ASvp Column Temperature Oven, API 3200. All the components of the system are controlled using CBM-20AD System Controller. Data acquisition was done using Analyst 1.5.1 software. The ESI is operated in positive ion mode Chromatographic separations were accomplished using a Inertsil C₁₈, 5 µm, 50 mm×4.6 mm column. The mobile phase consists of a mixture of 10 parts of 5mM ammonium acetate solution and 90 parts of Acetonitrile. The mixture was filtered through 0.22 µm membrane (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) under vacuum, and then degassed by flushing with nitrogen for 15 min. The mobile phase was pumped isocratically at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min during analysis, at ambient temperature. The rinsing solution consists of a mixture of 90: 10 % v/v of methanol: HPLC Grade Water. The cooler of the autosampler is set 10 °C. The run time of analysis is 2.5 minutes.

Preparation of Standard Solutions

A stock solution of propranolol is prepared in methanol such that the final concentration is approximately 1.0 mg/mL. Stock solution of tramadol (approx 1 mg/mL) is prepared in HPLC Grade methanol. The solutions were stored at 4°C and they were stable for at least two weeks. Aqueous stock dilution of propranolol is prepared in diluent solution (mixture of 50: 50 % v/v of methanol: HPLC Grade water).

Sample Preparation

Aqueous stock dilutions were prepared initially. 0.5 ml of each aqueous stock dilution is transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask. The final volume is made up with screened drug-free K₂EDTA human plasma and mixed gently for 15 minutes to achieve the desired concentration of calibration curve standards. The final calibration standard concentrations are 0.0 (Blank; no propranolol added), 1.000, 2.000, 25.000, 100.543, 201.085, 274.454, 350.541 and 402.171ng/ml. Each of these standard solutions was distributed in disposable polypropylene micro centrifuge tubes (1.5 ml, eppendorf) in volume of 0.6 ml and stored at -70°C until analysis. Similarly quality control samples were prepared in plasma such that the final concentrations were 1.044, 2.984, 165.760 and 290.759 ng/ml respectively and labeled as Lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), Low quality control (LQC), median quality control (MQC) and high quality control (HQC) respectively.

Extraction procedure

The extraction of the plasma samples involved Solid-Phase Extraction process. For processing, the stored spiked samples were withdrawn from the freezer and allowed to thaw at room temperature. An aliquot of 500 µL is then transferred to pre-labeled polypropylene RIA Vials. 25 µL of internal standard dilution (100 ng/mL) is then added and mixed.

Oasis HLB Cartridges (30mg/1cc) were then conditioned with 1.0 ml of methanol followed by 1.0 ml of water. The sample is then loaded and allowed to elute using positive pressure nitrogen. The cartridges are then washed with 1.0 ml of water followed by 1.0 ml of washing solution (5% v/v methanol). The drug and Internal standard are then allowed to elute into reagent vials using 2.0 ml of methanol. The eluate is then allowed to evaporate to dryness at 40°C using a constant pressure nitrogen evaporator. The dried residue is then reconstituted using 300 µl of mobile phase and vortexed for 2 minutes before transferring into HPLC vials for analysis.

Method Validation

The quantitative method was validated to determine selectivity, calibration range, accuracy and precision, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantitation, % recovery, short term, long term, freeze–thaw, and auto sampler stability. The initial assay was fully validated for Propranolol analysis in human plasma according to FDA guidelines.

Selectivity

The selectivity of the method was evaluated by analyzing six independent drug-free K₂EDTA human plasma samples with reference to potential interferences from endogenous and environmental constituents.

Calibration curve

Calibration curves were generated to confirm the relationship between the peak area ratios and the concentration of Propranolol in the standard samples. Fresh calibration standards were extracted and assayed as described above on three different days and in duplicate. Calibration curves for Propranolol were represented by the plots of the peak-area ratio (Propranolol / Tramadol) versus the nominal concentration of the Propranolol in calibration standards. The regression line was generated using 1/concentration² factor as the mathematical model of best fit. Propranolol concentrations in QC samples, recovery, and stability samples were calculated from the resulting area ratio and the regression equation of the calibration curve.

Accuracy and precision

Intra-day accuracy and precision were evaluated by analysis of QCs at four levels (LLOQ, LQC, MQC and HQC; n = 6 at each level) on the same day. Inter-day precision and the accuracy were determined by analyzing four QC levels on 3 separate days (n = 6 at each level) along with three separate standard curves done in duplicates.

The accuracy of an analytical method describes how close the mean test results obtained by the method are to the nominal concentration of the analyte. Accuracy was calculated by the following equation, expressed as a percentage:

$$\text{Accuracy (\%)} = \text{mean observed concentration/nominal concentration} \times 100$$

The precision was expressed by co-efficient of variation (CV). The CV % indicates the variability around the mean in relation to the size of the mean, and is defined as:

$$\text{CV (\%)} = \text{standard deviation/mean observed concentration} \times 100$$

Stability Studies

Autosampler, and freeze–thaw stability of Propranolol was determined at low, medium and high QC concentrations. Bench top (9 hrs at room temperature), long term stability of the plasma matrix (10 days at –70 °C) is evaluated. To determine the impact of freeze–thaw cycles on Propranolol concentration, samples were allowed to undergo 4 freeze (–70 °C) thaw (room temperature) cycles. Following sample treatment/storage conditions, the Propranolol concentrations were analyzed in triplicates and compared to the control sample that had been stored at –70 °C. Autosampler stability of extracted samples was determined by comparing Propranolol concentration in freshly prepared samples and samples kept in autosampler at 4 °C for 48 hrs. Aqueous solutions of Propranolol and internal standard were also evaluated for bench top stability (8 hrs at room temperature) and refrigerated stability for 8 days.

Recovery

Recovery was determined by comparing the area under the curve (AUC) of extracted QC samples (LQC, MQC and HQC) with direct injection of extracted blank plasma spiked with the same nominal concentration of Propranolol as in the QC samples. This should highlight any loss in signal due to the extraction process. IS recovery was similarly calculated.

Data analysis

Data acquisition and processing was performed by Analyst 1.5.1 software. Standard curves for quantitation of Propranolol were constructed using a 1/concentration² weighted linear regression of the peak area ratio versus Propranolol concentration. Unknown and QC sample concentrations were back-calculated from the standard curves.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Method Development

The ESI-MS is optimized in a view to develop a sensitive and reproducible method for the determination of Propranolol in Human Plasma. In the ESI process the molecules are subjected to a high degree of induced polarization by the application of Ion spray voltage which is usually a magnitude of 3000 – 5500 V. Depending on the polarity of the ion spray voltage the molecule undergoes protonation or deprotonation to form an ion. Conceptually, acidic molecules are electron pair acceptors and therefore ionize in the negative ion mode. Similarly basic molecules tend to ionize in positive ion mode [20]. In the current method positive ion mode is

chosen for the ion spray voltage because it resulted in higher response. A summary of the chromatographic conditions and ionization parameters is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Optimized Chromatographic Conditions and Mass Parameters

Chromatographic conditions		Ionization Parameters	
Column Name	Inertsil, 50 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ	Ion spray Voltage	5500 V
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Buffer Solution ::90:10, v/v	Curtain gas	7.00
Column Oven temperature	40 $^{\circ}$ C	Heater temperature	450 $^{\circ}$ C
Auto-Sampler Temperature	10 $^{\circ}$ C	GS 1	30.00
Injection Volume	5 μ L	GS 2	40.00
Flow Rate	0.6 ml/minute	CAD Gas	5.00
Run Time	2.5 minutes	Interface heater	ON

Drug Name	Q1 Mass	Q3 Mass	Dwell (msec)	Time	Compound Parameters	Start	Stop
Propranolol	260.0	155.2	200		Declustering Potential (DP)	7.00	7.00
					Collision Cell Entrance Potential (CEP)	2.16	2.16
					Collision Energy	5.00	5.00
Tramadol	264.2	58.1	200		Declustering Potential (DP)	6.00	6.00
					Collision Cell Entrance Potential (CEP)	4.70	4.70
					Collision Energy	8.00	8.00

Table 2: Results of regression analysis of the linearity data

Summary of Calibration Curve Characteristics For Propranolol				
Replicate ID	Y intercept	Slope	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Regression Coefficient (r ²)
1	0.00126	0.0140	0.9955	0.9910
2	0.00118	0.0135	0.9965	0.9930
3	0.00128	0.0134	0.9975	0.9950
N	3	3	3	3
Mean	0.00124	0.01363	0.9965	0.9930

Table 3: Intra and Inter day accuracy and precision

	Nominal Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	LLOQ QC	LQC	MQC	HQC
ng/ml	1.044	2.984	165.760	290.759
Precision and Accuracy Batch – 1				
Mean Accuracy (n=6) Day 1	92.25	99.74	107.14	105.91
S.D.	0.05	0.08	3.18	7.30
% CV	5.44	2.85	1.79	2.37
Precision and Accuracy Batch – 2				
Mean Accuracy (n=6) Day 2	93.21	99.63	106.88	103.36
S.D.	0.03	0.16	5.00	5.17
% CV	3.29	5.29	2.82	1.72
Precision and Accuracy Batch – 3				
Mean Accuracy (n=6) Day 3	95.36	101.41	108.46	105.42
S.D.	0.06	0.10	2.23	4.52
% CV	6.42	3.20	1.24	1.47

To facilitate the ionization process, the mobile phase is prepared such that it contains 10 parts of 5 mM Ammonium acetate. Acidic mobile phase tends to ionize the basic molecules thus resulting in better and stable response. Extraction methods were initially attempted using Protein precipitation technique. Precipitation technique was adopted using Acetonitrile and or Methanol. Initial experiments of protein precipitation were done using 1: 3 ratio of plasma : Organic solvents. The recovery of the Propranolol is moderate while that of the internal standard is relatively unchanged but resulted in a high degree of noise during detection. Matrix effects are also significant.

Although Propranolol and internal standard are highly non-polar and are suitable for extraction using the liquid-liquid extraction technique, it appeared that the –OH groups of both the drug and internal standard can be bitterly entrapped in the bonded phase of solid phase extraction cartridge when Solid phase extraction is used. Initial experiments were performed by using non-polar solvents like t-butyl methyl ether, dichloromethane and diethyl ether. Compared to the liquid-liquid extraction, SPE proved to improve the recovery and a better matrix clean up during the extraction. SPE was therefore finalized using the OASIS HLB 30mg/1cc cartridges.

Initial experiments employing conventional flow rates of 0.5-0.7 ml/min resulted in optimal retention times for Propranolol. The run time of analysis is approximately 2.5 minutes when an Inertsil ODS reverse phase column (50 X 4.6 mm id, C₁₈, 5 micron) is used. Also the organic composition of the mobile phase is kept at 90% v/v.

The column temperature is maintained at ambient. At the reported flow rate, peak shape was acceptable. There was no interference in the drug and internal standard, from the extracted blank. The use of volatile buffers for mass spectral analysis has been discussed elsewhere [16]. Acetate buffer and formate buffers were initially used for the experiment. 5mM Ammonium acetate buffer resulted in better ionization response. Since the noise effects in solid phase extraction (SPE) method are almost removed, we have done the final analysis using SPE technique.

Detection and chromatography

Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows the typical mass spectra of Propranolol and Tramadol. The multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) scan for Propranolol indicated a parent ion of 260.0 (Q1) and product ion (Q3) as 155.2. The transition (Q1/Q3) is found to be 260.0 / 155.2 Da is taken for final analysis. The multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) scan for Tramadol indicated a parent ion of 264.2 (Q1) and product ion 58.1 (Q3). The stable transition (Q1/Q3) is found to be 264.2 / 58.1 Da is taken for the internal standard. The retention times for Propranolol and Tramadol were 1.63 and 1.31 min, respectively.

Figure 1: Structure of PROPRANOLOL and TRAMADOL

Figure 2: Typical MRM scan spectra for Propranolol showing parent and product ions

Figure 3: Typical MRM scan spectra for TRAMADOL showing parent and product ions

Figure-4: Representative chromatograms of Blank, Zero blank, LQC and HQC

Method validation

Calibration curves

A system suitability exercise is performed before the initiation of the validation. A system is assumed to be suitable for analysis if and only if the % CV for the retention times of Propranolol and internal standards is less than 2 %. For preparation of pooled plasma for the validation, six different lots of blank plasma were screened for specificity. The chromatograms are represented in **Figure – 4**. All the lots were found to have no significant endogenous interferences at the retention times of the analyte and the internal standard. The same human EDTA plasma lots free of interfering substances were used to prepare the calibration curve standards and the quality control samples for the validation study.

Calibration curves for Propranolol in human plasma were fitted by weighted $1/\text{concentration}^2$ quadratic regression, with the r^2 values of >0.99 for all curves generated during the validation. The results are presented in **Table 2**. All the standards demonstrated an accuracy within $\pm 3\%$ of their respective nominal concentrations. Results were calculated using peak area ratios.

Accuracy and precision

A detailed summary of the intra-day and inter-day precision and accuracy data generated for the assay validation is presented in **Table 3**. Inter-assay variability was expressed as the accuracy and precision of the mean QC concentrations (LLOQ, LQC, MQC,

and HQC) of three separate assays. Intra-assay variability was determined as the accuracy and precision of the six individual QC concentrations within one assay. The inter- and intra-assay accuracy and precision for all QC concentrations is within the acceptable limit recommended by the USFDA [17].

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

LOD is defined as the lowest concentration that produced a peak distinguishable from background noise (minimum ratio of 3:1). The approximate LOD was 0.263 µg/mL. The LLOQ has been accepted as the lowest points on the standard curve with a relative standard deviation of less than 20% and signal to noise ratio of 5:1. Results at lowest concentration studies (0.263 µg/m) met the criteria for the LLOQ QC (Table 3). The method was found to be sensitive for the determination of Propranolol in human plasma samples. The ULOQ has been accepted as the highest points on the standard curve with a relative standard deviation of less than 15%.

Carryover test

A critical issue with the analysis of many drugs is their tendency to get adsorbed by reversed phase octa-decyl-based chromatographic packing materials, resulting in the carryover effect. However in this analysis no quantifiable carryover effect was obtained when a series of blank (plasma) solutions were injected immediately following the highest calibration standard.

Stability studies

The results of bench top, long term, autosampler and freeze–thaw stability are presented in Table 4. Determination of Propranolol stability following three freeze–thaw cycles showed that for all QC samples there was a no significant change in the Propranolol concentration. The stability of the aqueous solutions of Propranolol and the internal standard were also represented in Table-5a and Table 5b respectively. Under refrigerated conditions there is no significant change in the concentration of the samples.

Table 4: Short Term, long term and Freeze Thaw stability of Propranolol (n=6) represented as % stability

	% Accuracy(n=6)	
	LQC	HQC
Bench top stability (9 Hours)	98.91	103.91
Long-term stability (11 Days)	100.48	100.42
Freeze – Thaw stability (4 Cycles)	99.24	104.23
Autosampler stability (48 hrs)	99.27	104.25

Table 5a: Bench top and refrigerated stability of Propranolol and Tramadol in stock solution

Propranolol Injection No.	AQS STD 08 Response		Tramadol AQS STD 08 Response	
	Fresh Stock	Room Temp. Stock Solution	Fresh Stock	Room Temp. Stock Solution
1	1363750	1365670	928260	928629
2	1377627	1378349	938415	930552
3	1372536	1365767	937272	925825
4	1365612	1375329	935127	928153
5	1370421	1377228	939600	920244
6	1374770	1357592	938226	924152
N	6	6	6	6
Average	1370786	1369989.2	936150.0	926259.2
Standard Deviation	5331.84	8258	4144.88	3699.78
CV (Precision %)	0.39	0.60	0.44	0.40
% Stability	99.87		98.97	
% Change (100 - % Stability)	0.13		1.03	
Stock Concentration	401.89	402.17	201.01	200.95
Correction Factor	0.9993		1.0003	

Table 5b: Long-term stability of Propranolol and Tramadol in stock solution

Injection No.	Propranolol			Tramadol		
	AQS STD 08 Response			AQS STD 08 Response		
	Fresh Stock	Refrigerator Solution	Stock	Fresh Stock	Refrigerator Solution	Stock
1	1593756	1619988		1079898	1086553	
2	1599494	1644714		1071497	1089036	
3	1605693	1641306		1073281	1086778	
4	1635665	1626270		1076820	1085449	
5	1612530	1631969		1083580	1092320	
6	1618586	1637581		1072908	1081961	
N	6	6		6	6	
Average	1610954.0	1633638.0		1076330.7	1087016.2	
Standard Deviation	15007.64	9385.29		4688.23	3478.29	
CV (Precision %)	0.93	0.57		0.44	0.32	
% Stability	101.17			100.53		
% Change (100 - % Stability)	-1.16			-0.98		
Stock Concentration	401.24	402.17		200.04	200.95	
Correction Factor	0.9977			0.9954		

Recovery

Percentage recovery of Propranolol was measured by dividing the peak area values of extracted QC samples with direct injection of solution containing the same nominal concentration of compounds as the QC samples in extracted blank plasma. The mean recovery of Propranolol at LQC, MQC and HQC levels was 41.5 %, 46.6 % and 47.8 % respectively. The overall recovery is 45.29 % with a % Coefficient of variation of 7.5 %, respectively. The recovery of internal standard is 74.28 % at MQC level concentration of Propranolol.

CONCLUSION

A HPLC-ESI-MS method was developed and validated for the determination of Propranolol in human plasma. The extraction process was a single-step liquid-liquid extraction procedure employing the use of 70: 30 methyl-t-butyl ether and dichloromethane. LLE method is usually devoid of polar interferences thus rendering the sample clean for final analysis. The noise is usually absent or at minimum as compared to precipitation or SPE techniques. There is no carryover effect. Due to the LLE method of extraction, baseline noise is minimal. Matrix effects are not observed. In conclusion, method validation following FDA guideline indicated that the developed method had high sensitivity with an LLOQ of approximately 0.263 µg/mL, acceptable recovery, stability, specificity and excellent efficiency with a total running time of 2.0 min per sample, which is important for large batches of samples. Thus this method can be suitable for pharmacokinetic, bioavailability or bioequivalence studies of Propranolol in human subjects.

REFERENCES

1. A. J. Boakes, B. N. C. Prichard. The effect of AH 5158, pindolol, propranolol, D-propranolol on acute exercise tolerance in angina pectoris. *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1973, 47: 673-674.
2. A. Mitrani, M. Oettinger, E. G. Alunader, et al. Use of propranolol in Dysfunctional labour. *Br. J. Obstet. Gynecol.*, 1975, 82: 651-655.
3. K. L. Granville-Grossman, P. Turner. The effect of propranolol on anxiety. *Lancet*, 1966, 1: 788-790.
4. J. A. Murillo-Pulgarin, A. Alanon-Molina, P. Fernandez- Lopez. Simultaneous determination of atenolol, propranolol, dipyridamole and amiloride by means of non-linear variable angle synchronous fluorescence spectrometry. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1998, 370: 9-18.
5. C. Rodriguez Bueno, Dopaje, Mc-Graw Hill, Madrid, 1992.
6. T. Walle, T. Fagan, D. Conrad, et al. Presystemic and systemic glucosidation of propranolol. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.*, 1979, 76: 167-172.
7. J. A. P. Douglas, N. S. Baber, A. Lee. Once daily propranolol in the treatment of mild to moderate hypertension. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 1978, 14: 163-166.
8. A. Halkin, D. Vered, A. Saginer, et al. Once daily administration of sustained release propranolol capsules in the treatment of angina pectoris. *Eur. J. Clin. Pharmacol.*, 1979, 16: 387-391.
9. J. S. Floras, J. V. Jones, M. O. Hassan, et al. Ambulatory blood pressure during once-daily randomized double blind administration of atenolol, metoprolol, pindolol, and slow release propranolol. *Br. Med. J.*, 1982, 285: 1387-1392.
10. B. G. Charles, P. J. Ravenscroft, P. J. Renshaw. Comparative pharmacokinetics of propranolol and h-hydroxypropranolol using conventional and long acting propranolol. *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1982, 34: 481-484.
11. J. G. Wagner. Propranolol: pooled Michailins-Menter parameters and the effect of input rate of bioavailability. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.*, 1985, 37: 481-487.

12. I. R. Martinez, M. C. G. A. Coque, R. M. V. Camanas. Liquid chromatographic procedure for the evaluation of β -blockers in pharmaceuticals using hybrid micellar mobile phases. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1997, 765: 221-231.
13. Y. S. El-Saharty. Simultaneous high-performance liquid chromatographic assay of furosemide and propranolol HCl and its application in a pharmacokinetic study, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2003, 33: 699-709.
14. S. B. Black, A. M. Stenhouse, R. C. Hansson. Solid-phase extraction and derivatisation methods for β -blockers in human post mortem whole blood, urine and equine urine. *J. Chromatogr. B*, 1996, 685: 67-80.
15. P. Hubert, P. Chiap, M. Moors, et al. Knowledge-based system for the automated solid-phase extraction of basic drugs from plasma coupled with their liquid chromatographic determination: Application to the biodetermination of β -receptor blocking agents. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1994, 665: 87-99.
16. F. F. T. Verves, H. G. Schaefer, J. T. Lefevre, et al. Simultaneous assay of propranolol, diltiazem and metabolites of diltiazem in human plasma by liquid chromatography. *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1990, 8: 535-539.
17. Dalibor Satinsky, Hugo S. Serralheiro, Petr Solich, et al. On-line coupling of sequential injection extraction with restricted-access materials and post-column derivatization for sample clean-up and determination of propranolol in human plasma. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, 600: 122-128.
18. R.J. Ruane, I.D. Wilson. Ion-pair reversed-phase thin-layer chromatography of basic drugs using sulphonic acids. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1988, 441 355-360.
19. I. Zelikman, S. Hjerten. Determination of total and free concentration of propranolol in human plasma by displacement electrophoresis in a two-layer polyacrylamide gel using fluorimetric detection. *Biomed. Chromatogr.*, 1989, 3161-3165.
20. W. F. Smyth. Recent studies on the electrospray ionization mass spectrometric behaviour of selected nitrogen-containing drug molecules and its application to drug analysis using liquid chromatography–electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry. *J Chromatogr B*. 2005, 824: 1–20.
21. Guidance for Industry, Bioanalytical Method Validation, US Department of Health and Human Services, Food and Drug Administration, Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER), May 2001.

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